

***Proreus simulans* (Dermaptera:Chelisochidae), a predator of rice leaffolder and skipper larvae**

A. T. Barrion and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Adult *P. simulans* (Stål), an important earwig predator of oriental maize borer *Ostrinia furnacalis* (Guenée) larvae, were collected from flooded, rainfed lowland rice fields at Brooke's Point, Palawan, Philippines. They were found inside leaves folded by *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) and within the feeding chambers (groups of leaves joined by silk) of rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias* (F.). Larvae were consumed whole, partially eaten, or injured by *P. simulans* forceps.

P. simulans is about 19 mm long with red-brown lateral margins on the wing covers (elytra) and yellow legs with fine hairs (see figure). *P. simulans* was previously thought to inhabit upland environments, notably sugarcane fields, from which they enter maize fields to reproduce. At Brooke's Point, no sugar-cane was near the rice fields. Tall grasses, dominated by *Scirpus grossus* L., were noted in nearby swampy areas and may serve as the refuge of the predator.

P. simulans kills larvae with the long forceps that it projects forward over its body by arching its abdomen. The male has a prominent pair of spines on the inside of the forceps.

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